

and cation exchange capacity 10.0 meq/100 g.

Rice was transplanted 14 Jul. Soils had adequate available P and K, but all varieties received 150 kg N/ha as urea in 3 equal splits (at transplanting and at 25 and 50 d after transplanting) and 25 kg ZnSO₄/ha at transplanting. The experiment had four replications.

In Karnal, P2-21 was harvested 1 Oct, Jaya and IR8 were harvested 26 Oct, and CSRI was harvested 11 Nov. Sodic soil at Gudda delayed maturity and the same varieties were harvested on 14 Oct and 10 and 18 Nov.

Yields of Jaya and IR8 were similar at Karnal, and were significantly more than that of P2-21, which yielded significantly

more than CSRI (see table). On sodic soil, however, Jaya, IR8, and P2-21 yielded similarly and were significantly inferior to CSRI.

All varieties yielded much less in sodic soils than in semireclaimed sodic soil. The mean pH of the sodic soil decreased from 10.5 to 10.2 because of rice cultivation. □

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Yield characters for cold-tolerant rice

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We studied yield-related characters for cold-tolerant rice at the VLHA, 1,300 m above sea level. Each of 380 entries included in the third International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery was transplanted at 20-cm spacing in nonreplicated plots in three 3-m-long rows.

Some cultures suffered severe post-anthesis cold damage, and only 225 entries were observed for yield. Plant height, tillers/plant, panicles/plant, grains/panicle, % fertile spikelets/panicle,

1,000-grain weight, grain and straw yield, and harvest index were recorded and evaluated by correlation and path analyses.

Yield/plant was significantly and positively correlated with number of tillers (0.36), number of panicles (0.39), straw yield (0.25), and harvest index (0.69). Straw yield was significantly and positively correlated with plant height (0.29), number of tillers (0.30), and grains/panicle (0.20). Grains/panicle and % fertility had positive and significant correlation (0.37). Number of panicles was positively and significantly correlated (0.24) with harvest index, but negatively and significantly correlated with grains/panicle (-0.31), % fertility (-0.31), and 1,000-grain weight (-0.27). Number of tillers was negatively and significantly

correlated with grains/panicle (-0.20), % spikelet fertility (-0.28), and 1,000-grain weight (-0.23). The association of plant height and straw was negative and significant (-0.24), as was plant height and number of panicles (-0.23).

Path analysis showed that panicles/plant had maximum direct and indirect effect on grain yield. Grains/panicle, spikelet fertility, and 1,000 grain weight also had direct effects on yield, but those were counterbalanced by a negative indirect effect of panicles/plant.

Results indicate that breeding to develop high yielding, cold-tolerant rices should emphasize number of panicle-bearing tillers/plant, high grains/panicle, good spikelet fertility, and high harvest index. □

Varietal tolerance for low temperature and influence of planting dates and nitrogen fertilization

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From 1979-81 dry seasons, 463 entries from the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were screened for vegetative stage tolerance for 16-20°C temperatures. Seeds were sown 14 Oct and transplanted 15 Nov. Seedlings of each line were planted 2/hill in a 5-m-long plot with 4 rows spaced at 25 × 25 cm. NPK was applied at 120-40-40 kg/ha, with N applied in 3 equal splits.

Ten promising entries were selected

Table 1. Agronomic characters of 10 outstanding entries selected from 463 entries in the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery; 1979-81 dry season (Nov-Mar)^a Badeggi, Nigeria.

Entry	Yield (t/ha)	Maturity (d)	Plant ht (cm)	Spikelet fertility	Panicle exertion	Phenotypic acceptability
RPKN-2	4.4	115	118	X	X	X
B2012C-KN-15-1-3-2-3	5.6	121	122	X	X	X
KULU	4.8	121	119	X	X	X
KN-361-BKK-27-1	4.4	115	118	X	X	X
IR9202-36-3-2	6.0	139	100	X	X	X
B737F-KN-10-3-1-2	5.6	118	120	X	X	X
IR9202-25-1-3	7.2	120	108	X	X	X
IR8965-K1	6.0	122	77	X	X	X
IR9224-K1	6.0	106	94	X	X	X
IR9202-22-3-2	6.8	139	99	X	X	X

^ax = promising entries.

(Table 1) for further field evaluation on the basis of plant height, growth duration, tiller number, leaf color, panicle emergence, flowering uniformity, spikelet

sterility, phenotypic acceptability, grain size, and grain yield.

The 1982 performance of the entries was evaluated at three planting dates and